

Advocating Women Dispositions in the Plays of Shakespeare

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In the majority of Shakespeare’s works, women appear as sustaining and vital characters. They always manipulate and influence characters and are also underestimated in certain circumstances. A woman in Shakespeare’s plays has vital roles and sometimes the leading roles. They usually create main conflicts and acts as the base of his plays as they bring up moral and cultural questions upon the prevailing social situation. In Shakespeare’s period, a woman only has little choice in many important decisions of their life. People during that time have loved the girls who the rules by their father and after marriage women financially depending on her husband by law. The present study compares some of the Heroine characters of Shakespeare to give a clear portrait of the women during the Elizabethan age.

In discrepancy to his period Shakespeare portrays his woman characters, as powerful, rebellious and independent there are also naive women portrayed in his plays, like Cordelia in King Lear and Desdemona in Othello, they try to follow society’s ideal type of women; yet this often ends the plot virtuous, however, they all die in the end. Official schooling for girls in Shakespeare’s day ends when they are young. Education for the girls during Shakespeare’s age was limited for only their domestic awareness to manage a household. His plays had some uneducated women characters like the bawdy Nurse in the play Romeo and Juliet who is not considered to be suitable for a wife.

In the famous play, King Lear devious daughters of Lear, Goneril and Regan confront him about their unlimited love for him, so that they can take over the kingdom from him. At last, they neglect their father for political power and make him insane. Othello, the well-known tragic play, deals with the love life of an upper-class woman and a black man. The heroine of this play is Desdemona, who is innocent and very loving towards her husband Othello. She is wrongly accused of adultery and killed in the hands of her loving husband. Trickery and charm also to magic and witches, a commonly occurring theme in Shakespeare’s day. The devious Lady Macbeth in the play Macbeth, Lady Macbeth is clearly very different from society’s ideal obedient, passive wife.

Flavours of Literature

Lady Macbeth is considered as a very tough woman. She utilizes her gender as a woman and plots evil against King Duncan and influences Macbeth to kill him. She ridicules Macbeth for his hesitant to kill the king, and mock his lack of courage. In general, women had a hard time in Shakespeare's day.

Cordelia in King Lear is one of the good examples for the Elizabethan women, who was underestimated and ruined by the regulations of the social order. The play mediates about the unsuccessful and imprudent Lear, who comes to a decision to retreat as a king and plans to bestow his properties to his three daughters based on the perimeter of their love towards him. Goneril and Regan, the elder daughters of Lear, exaggerate their love with their insincere proclamation. Cordelia the youngest of all and the obedient child exclaims that she adores him as a normal daughter to her father. This declaration of Cordelia disappointed Lear and infuriated; he expels her from the country, announces to her suitors that anyone of them can have her, but without the offering, they had been expecting. Yet the King of France was willing to marry her for herself. Later, when the other two sisters have cruelly abandoned Lear, she is with him; also captivated, she comforts him. Cordelia portrayed a strong self-determining character all through the play, even while her sisters have her hanged, Lear realizes about his mistake and dies of a broken heart.

Portia, in The Merchant of Venice, is one of the most prominent and mature woman characters of Shakespeare. Portia comes as a disguised young male judge and shows her extraordinary qualities by delivering judgment to protect Antonio from Shylock, the duke of Venice. They are a resident of the imbalanced society for women; Shakespeare mostly portrayed his female characters to be appreciated and conveying about their own opinions. In the civilization where the women were not considered to speak or act, Shakespeare gives them voice and action through his plays.

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